

Chemistry applications and programs on the personal computer (Macintosh)

David Kipp

Year 11, University High School
Parkville, Victoria

1. Introduction

This report is a part of my participation in the 1993 CSIRO Student Research Scheme, the project title being *Molecular Chemistry on the Supercomputer*. As an introduction to the project, it was decided that I start off researching smaller programs for the personal computer, rather than large supercomputational programs, which I will study later on in the project.

The aim of this report is to give a summary of the various computer programs and applications available in the study of chemistry today, which can be accessed from computer network archives around the world.

It is aimed at anyone with a personal computer, in this case a Macintosh, but primarily at secondary school teachers who wish to provide a broader range of learning tools for their students.

It is also intended to serve as a guide for obtaining these programs from world networks.

To obtain these applications, it is necessary to obtain access to a computer which can access world networks. This can be done at any AARNet site. AARNet is short for Australian Academic Research Network, and can be used by making the appropriate enquiries at your local university, asking for the AARNet administrator.

Schools can also set up links to the world "Internet" by subscribing to a commercial service (eg. Compuserve), by setting up a FIDOnet node, or dialling to a public access site. For information on the Internet system, see section 3.1 below.

There are basically two types of chemistry programs available for the Macintosh:

- HyperCard stack applications;
- Molecular modelling programs.

The main focus of this report is those programs which can be obtained free-of-charge, or as shareware, from world networks, and which I have found myself. For information on other software, one can consult the Directory of Chemistry Software (see reference 6, section 4.)

Hypercard stack applications are available on the Macintosh, and can take the form of tutorials, quiz programs, or databases. They are designed to teach fundamental principles of chemistry, and can be very useful for students.

Molecular modelling applications are programs which enable the user to visualise different molecules or lattices from a library of molecules, and to rotate or manipulate them on the screen. Programs such as this include

MacMolecule 1.7, for the Macintosh. Here there can be a variety of display options, such as wire-frame, ball-and-stick, or space-filling.

There is a third category of programs available; these, however, are not within the scope of this report. These are large commercial programs, and are not generally available for downloading from world network archives; these must be bought from companies for the appropriate price. However, it is possible to see how these programs operate, by making the appropriate enquiries at places like CSIRO. Tools like this include UniChem, the latest state-of-the-art quantum chemistry program, Discover, and DMol.

However, many programs of the first two types can be accessed from file archives around the world. There are many ways of accessing these files. Programs such as Fetch, for the Macintosh, access global networks, through a central file-server. Other fetching programs include Gopher or TurboGopher. *Note:* Fetch and TurboGopher will only work if your Macintosh has a TCP/IP or SLIP connection to the world networks. Other programs are needed for other connection types.

To connect to an archive computer, it is possible to use a computer connected to an AARNet location via TCP/IP, and then to open a connection, through a central file-server. You can also access the archives by using the ftp command if you have a UNIX account and have a TCP/IP connection installed. The address for /umich is archive.umich.edu. For /infomac, it is: sumex-aim.stanford.edu. However, from Australian sites it is more efficient and faster to connect to a local "mirror" site of those archive sites. The Internet address of the Australian mirror site is:archie.au. Therefore you would type: *ftp archie.au*. You login as *anonymous* and type your internet address as a password.

There are a number of directories (folders) to choose from here; the relevant programs, however, are under the /micros/mac/ subdirectory. For a brief description of the UNIX directory structure, see section 1.1 below. The majority of programs concerning chemistry can usually be found on the directories /infomac and /umich. On the /infomac directory, there are three relevant subdirectories you can search on:

- /card. This directory contains mainly HyperCard stack applications, including chemistry applications;

- /demos. This directory contains demonstrations of Macintosh applications, all of which give an example of what can be achieved with the application; and

- /app. This contains the majority of applications.

On the /umich (University of Michigan) subdirectory, the relevant directory is /hypercard/util/science.

Having found the desired application or program, it is then possible to download this program and then copy it onto floppy disk, for use on a personal Macintosh. All this can be done free of charge, since the majority of programs mentioned here are public domain. Some are shareware, though, and require a small charge.

1.1. UNIX Directory Structure

In Fetch, files are grouped in different folders, or directories. To access a directory, double-click on its icon. The path name (directory name) is displayed in a small box above the list of available directories. When you first enter Fetch, this displays the root directory, denoted by a slash (/). As you move further down the hierarchy, you can click and hold on this directory box to view a list of the directories you have opened. To open any of these directories, click on it. For example, to open the folder `/micros/mac/info-mac/card`, the following steps are taken:

1. In the root directory, double-click on the `/micros` icon. This will open the `/micros` folder.
2. In the `/micros` directory, double-click on the `/mac` icon. Continue like this until you reach the directory you want.

1.2. Public-Access UNIX Systems in Melbourne

If you have a modem attached to your computer, you can access UNIX systems in Melbourne. There are two:

1. werple 888 1726 (V.32bis)
2. zikzak 562 8814 (V.22bis)
 562 8813 (V.32bis)

Login as the user "register" and follow the dots.

2. Examples of Available Applications

2.1. HyperCard Stack Applications

Many of these applications can be accessed through Fetch, on the directory `/micros/mac/info-mac/card`.

2.1.1. Atoms

Atoms is a HyperCard stack which is in the format of a tutorial. It is designed to teach the fundamental principles of atomic structure, and, in my view, would be extremely useful for secondary school students. This is a full version with 30 cards (pages) in the stack, and is free. It would probably be more suited for Year 10 or Year 11 students. The application uses approximately 85K of space.

2.1.2. Periodic Table 1.1

Periodic Table 1.1 is a HyperCard stack in the form of a database, which enables the user to call up data on elements in the periodic table. The information shown includes properties such as melting point, boiling point, density, electronegativity, and thermodynamic properties. This would also be an extremely useful program for secondary students of all levels, however it

would also be very useful for anyone else with an interest in chemistry. This is a full version, and is free. It uses approximately 230K of space.

2.1.3. Bonding

Bonding is a HyperCard stack which is specifically designed for use by secondary school chemistry students, to test their understanding of the types of chemical bonding found in common compounds. Because it is designed with secondary school chemistry programs in mind, I found it also very useful. This application would be useful for students of about Year 11 standard. The program is free; it uses approximately 50K of space.

2.1.4. CrystalTutor Demo

CrystalTutor is a set of seven stacks illustrating some basic ideas of solid state structure and geometry. This demonstration stack includes segments which illustrate the style and content of the individual stacks. I didn't really find this stack to be as useful as the previous ones, but it would still be a good teaching aid. It is probably at about Year 12 standard. This version was only a demo; it uses approximately 275K of space.

2.1.5. Chemistry Chapter 1

This is a demonstration, in the form of a 'textbook' on chemistry. Chapter 1 summarises the basic ideas of the study of chemistry, while other chapters are available, which expand on different concepts. This would be an extremely useful computer tool, as it sets out basic ideas clearly and concisely, and in an easy-to-use format. It would be ideal for Years 9-11 students of chemistry. It uses approximately 45K of space.

2.1.6. The Elements

This application is much the same as 2.1.2, Periodic Table 1.1, in that it is a periodic table which allow the user to call up data on elements, and to view their properties, such as thermodynamic properties. The user can also sort through the elements in a particular order, eg. by density. Programs like this are useful tools to have; as with *Periodic Table 1.1*, I think it would be useful for anyone with an interest in chemistry, rather than just students of chemistry. It uses approximately 70K of space.

2.2. Molecular Modelling and Non-HyperCard Applications

Sources for these applications from Fetch include the directories:

- /micros/mac/info-mac/demo
- /micros/mac/info-mac/app

2.2.1. MacMolecule 1.7

MacMolecule 1.7 is a molecular modeller for the Macintosh. It allows the user to visualise small molecules on the screen. It allows different display modes (such as ball-and-stick or space-filling), and the user can rotate and manipulate the molecules. This would be a very useful program for secondary school students, as it enables students to easily visualise the structures of molecules, which is often a difficult topic. This application would be useful for all high school students. The application itself uses approximately 165K of space.

2.2.2. Lattice Maker 2.6

LatticeMaker 2.6 can be used with the programs Ball & Stick, Chem-3D and MacMolecule. It is designed to help in the production of images of large bulk structures, or super-structures of crystal lattices. This program wouldn't be a lot of use to secondary school students, but it is still interesting to use. The application uses approximately 200K of space.

2.2.3. Ball&StickDemo

Ball&StickDemo is a molecular graphics application for all Macintosh computers. The user can construct models of small molecules, or view them from a library of molecules. This demo version isn't really useful, as it only allows the user to watch two demo movies of molecules. The application uses approximately 335K of space.

2.2.4. ChemEdit

ChemEdit enables the user to create representations of organic molecules, complete with stereochemical detail. This is a useful tool in the study of organic chemistry, and would be of most use to VCE (Years 11 and 12) students. The application uses approximately 185K of space.

2.2.5. MacChemTab 2.0

MacChemTab is a database of the periodic table. The user can easily explore the relationships that exist between the elements; the database includes an option to visualise these relationships in a graph format. I found that this application was easy to use, and therefore would be ideal for the educational environment. As with the other periodic table applications, it would be useful for other interested people as well. It uses approximately 125K of space.

2.3. Large Commercial Programs

2.3.1. UniChem

CSIRO was the first site in Australia to install the UniChem package, from Cray Research, on its Cray Y-MP supercomputer. UniChem is an easy-to-use supercomputing environment for computational chemistry. The primary uses of UniChem are in chemical, pharmaceutical, petrochemical and chemical physics as well as in automotive, electronics or aerospace industries. UniChem

is a distributed environment: a graphical user interface resides on a Silicon Graphics workstation and the computational part on Cray supercomputers. The computational part of UniChem consists of three high-performance, state-of-the-art programs, each designed for specific types of calculations.

- MNDO90, a semi-empirical program applicable to molecules containing up to approximately 500 atoms, developed in Germany
- DGauss, a density functional program applicable to molecules and clusters containing up to 200 atoms, developed at Cray Research. DGauss is well suited for metals, transition metals and inorganic systems.
- CADPAC, a program developed at the University of Cambridge, applicable to systems containing up to 50 atoms.

2.3.2. BIOSYM Polymer Software Modelling Package

This is a set of polymer modelling tools for scientists working in advanced polymer research, provided as interactive, graphical simulation and analysis tools. The package uses computational chemistry techniques, and enables scientists to construct model polymer systems and to predict their properties.

2.3.3. BIOSYM Catalysis and Sorption Project

This is a project designed to address the needs of scientists in the field of catalyst and sorbent technology. Catalysis is the cornerstone of chemical, petrochemical and biochemical processes; sorption is a key method for isolating end products.

2.3.4. Chem-X

Chem-X is used by specialists and occasional users for chemical structure visualisation, computation and databases. The intuitive menus allow routine modelling tasks to be performed simply by inexperienced modellers. This has been achieved by the careful selection of appropriate default options and automation of calculations. This program is produced by Chemical Design.

2.3.5. Discover 3.1

Produced by Biosym Technologies, *Discover* is a molecular simulation program that performs molecular mechanics and dynamics computations. *Discover* provides tools for performing simulations under various conditions, including constant temperature and constant pressure.

2.3.6. DMol 2.3

Also produced by Biosym Technologies, *DMol* is a first-principles quantum chemistry software package that performs accurate theoretical calculations on a wide range of compounds, including metal clusters, biological compounds, organometallics, and organic compounds.

As I mentioned earlier, these programs cannot be obtained through global networks, and do cost money. However, it is possible to see some of these programs at work by enquiring at:

- CSIRO Division of Information Technology
 Supercomputing Support Group
 723 Swanston Street, Carlton, Vic. 3053, Australia
 Telephone: (03) 282 2621

Enquiries: Dr Marek T. Michalewicz (Email: marek@mel.dit.csiro.au)

2.4. Further References

As well as searching on world networks for chemistry programs, there are also books available which give lists of chemistry software. One such reference is the Directory of Chemistry Software, edited by Wendy Warr, Peter Willett, and Geoff Downs. This is an up-to-date reference for software used in chemistry, including molecular modelling, structural drawing, chemical structure searching, and quantum mechanics. There are a large number of chemistry programs for the Macintosh to be found in this reference, however, they are mostly commercial programs, and cost a fair amount of money. For example, Chem3D, a molecular modelling program for the Macintosh, is priced at US\$595 (A\$420).

3. Network Services

3.1. Internet Services

For information on obtaining Internet Access, you can check with the computer centre at any university to learn about the online facilities available to you.

3.2. Further Reading on Internet

The following references are further reading for more information about the Internet:

1. The Internet Companion. A Beginner's Guide To Global Networking. Tracy LaQuey, Jeanne C. Ryer; Addison-Wesley Publishing.
2. Internet: Mailing Lists 1993 Edition. Franklin F. Kuo, Series Editor; SRI Internet Information Services. Published by PTR Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
3. Internet: Getting Started. Franklin F. Kuo, Series Editor; SRI Internet Information Services. Published by PTR Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
4. The Whole Internet. Ed Krol; published by O'Reilly & Associates.
5. Zen & the Art of Internet. Brendan Kehoe; published by Prentice Hall.

4. Other References

6. Directory of Chemistry Software 1992, edited by Wendy Warr, Peter Willett and Geoff Downs; published by Cherwell Scientific Publishing and the American Chemical Society.

This is a reference for those programs which are not within the scope of this report.

5. Acknowledgements

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(final draft)